

An Open-Source Knowledge Graph Ecosystem for the Life Sciences

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The growth of biomedical data worldwide is exponential [1]. In the United States, the nearly universal adoption of electronic health records combined with the abundance of available Linked Open Biomedical Data and rapid advancements in next-generation sequencing technology have made tremendous amounts of data available for research [2,3]. These multimodal data capture different views that when properly combined, help characterize complex systems [4]. Unfortunately, these data are often highly distributed and heterogeneous, can be difficult to access due to licensing and privacy restrictions, lack interoperability, and often have inconsistent underlying models or representations, which limits most researchers from utilizing them in an integrated fashion [5,6].

Knowledge graphs (KGs) are used to integrate disparate data, decipher complex processes, and have frequently been used to systematically interrogate the biology underlying complicated systems and diseases [7]. Within the biological domain, KGs have been used to represent everything from metabolomics [9], cell signaling [10] and gene regulatory networks [11] to protein-protein networks [12], and drug interactions [13]. Within the clinical domain, KGs have largely been used to improve information retrieval for Question-Answering systems [14,15], capture complex patient information [16], and improve treatment recommendations [17]. While it is clear that KGs are a useful structure for integrating complex biomedical data, their value within the Life Sciences has yet to be fully realized. This is largely attributable to: (1) existing open source KG construction methods are unable to account for the use of different standardized terminologies or vocabularies, are technically complex, are difficult to use, and often perform poorly as the size of the resulting KG increases in scale [6,18]; (2) a lack of biologically and clinically meaningful benchmarks to evaluate resulting KGs; and (3) privacy concerns when leveraging external data with patient-level information.

To solve some of these KG construction challenges, we developed the PheKnowLator (Phenotype Knowledge Translator; <https://github.com/callahantiff/PheKnowLator>) Ecosystem, a suite of tools for constructing ontologically-grounded KGs built on FAIR Data Principles (i.e., Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reproducible [19]). The usability of the PheKnowLator Ecosystem is facilitated through copious documentation, Jupyter Notebook demos, and interactive scripts that guide users through the KG build process. Scalability within the PheKnowLator Ecosystem is achieved through parallelization of the build process and the fundamental principle that KGs represent biology and not metadata, ensuring that they are free of extraneous information. In addition to KG construction, the PheKnowLator Ecosystem provides monthly builds of open-source KGs designed to model the molecular mechanisms of human disease. The knowledge representation used to construct these builds was developed by a team of domain experts and took over three years of collaborative discussion and empirical experimentation to complete. The builds leverage 12 Open Biomedical Ontologies and over 30 publicly available resources producing KGs with 15 million nodes and 47 million edges.

Our presentation has two objectives. First, we will describe the PheKnowLator Ecosystem and our initial efforts to validate it. Then, we will present results and lessons learned from two biomedical applications using PheKnowLator KGs. The first application demonstrates how a KG can be used to integrate clinical observations with publicly available biological experiments to infer clinically meaningful and biologically-relevant unobserved patient-level molecular mechanisms. The second application describes our efforts to define meaningful heuristics to improve evidence-based recommendations for pharmacovigilance. We conclude by highlighting opportunities for KGs to solve real-world public health problems, such as automated adjudication and characterization of phenotypes, evidence-based feature selection for machine learning, and causal inference for pharmacovigilance.

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